

Cebuano nurses in non-nursing doctoral degrees

Brian A. Vasquez
Center for Research and Development
University of the Visayas
crpd@uv.edu.ph; brianquez@gmail.com

Republished from:

Vasquez, B. A. (2013). Cebuano nurses in non-nursing doctoral degrees. *Journal of Institutional Research, South East Asia*, 11(1), 42-57. (http://www.seairweb.info/journal/JIRSEA_v11_n1_2013.pdf#page=42)

ABSTRACT

Historically, a number of famous nurses finished non-nursing doctoral programs. The melting of different body of knowledge into the paradigms of nursing helped into the development of its own innovative frameworks. Inasmuch as these learnt concepts borrowed and shared from other discipline helped in the development of nursing theories, there is a need to recognize that doctoral education for nursing should be in nursing science. In Cebu City, Philippines, it was observed that nurses were taking doctoral programs that are not in the mainstream of nursing. It was the intention of this research to explore the lived-in experiences of these nurses and the reasons behind their choices utilizing Collaizi's seven steps data analysis. Furthermore, it attempted to identify the weaknesses, demands and scenario of the doctoral nursing offering in the area. Results revealed that: (1) nurses are forced to take non-nursing programs because of inaccessibility; (2) only one nursing school is offering a doctoral program and Gerontology is the sole major; (3) they tend to look for alternative programs that is related to their field of interest; (4) less access to scholarships for schooling in other places; and (5) there is a conflict in matching specific nursing interest with the non-nursing programs they are taking. With the call for transformation and advancement in nursing and its practice, nurses must grow professionally by taking doctoral program in different nursing concentrations and not with other or related disciplines.

Keywords: *nursing education, doctoral nursing program, advance studies, professional growth in nursing*

I. INTRODUCTION

Feeg and Nickitas (2011) claimed that there are less than one percent of nurses having doctoral degrees. This highlighted the critical need for doctorate prepared nurses that will educate future nurses. They are the workforces in generating evidence for practice that will meet the complex health needs of the clientele (Cronenwett, 2010). In America, some agencies advocate in

multiplying the number of doctorate prepared nurses that will be part of the pool of faculty and researchers (Institute of Medicine, 2010). In Asia, during the East Asian Forum on Nursing Scholars held last February 22 and 23, 2012 in Singapore, scholars conversed about the issue on advancing the doctoral nursing programs in East Asia. They significantly recognize its importance in contributing knowledge and evidence for the

nursing profession. In the Philippines, this issue is not much talked about and much more in Cebu City. Currently, only few literature talks about taking doctoral nursing degrees in the country. With not enough literature, there is a need to document the phenomenon, as this can be a virtuous source of reference.

The awareness required to deliver headship in the discipline of nursing is so multifaceted and swiftly moving that doctoral level education is necessary to prepare nurses in response to the emerging health care necessities (American Association of Colleges of Nursing, 2004). With this call for the transformation and advancement of nursing and its practice, nurses aspired to grow professionally by taking doctoral program in various nursing specializations. According to Romero (2011a), nurses with the highest educational attainment of a doctorate degree in nursing are prepared to be nurse scientists engaging massive knowledge in their field whether clinical, academe or administrative and most importantly research. Romero further added that they are expected to contribute in policy making and in shaping the healthcare system. However, the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002 (RA 9173) only requires a master's degree from middle to top nursing management level. The only position requiring a doctoral degree in nursing is doctorate-nursing professorship. With the current demand in work and competition in the field of nursing, Filipino nurses are increasingly expected to ascend the highest nursing educational preparation.

In Cebu City, Philippines, it was observed that nurses were taking doctoral programs that are not in the mainstream of nursing. Given this scenario, there is a conflict in matching specific nursing interest with the non-nursing programs they are taking. It is the intention of this research to explore the lived-in experiences of these nurses and the reasons behind their choices. Furthermore, it attempted to identify the weaknesses, demands and scenario of the doctoral nursing offerings in the area.

Historically, a number of famous nurses

finished non-nursing doctoral programs. Faye Glenn Adbellah, Imogen King and Hildegard Peplau finished Doctor of Education, Jean Watson finished PhD in Educational Psychology and Counseling, Betty Neuman received a Doctoral Degree in Clinical Psychology, Patricia Benner received a PhD in Stress, Coping and Health, Sister Calista Roy finished PhD in Sociology (Tomey & Alligood, 2002), and Madeleine Leininger finished PhD in Cultural and Social Anthropology (George, 2002). The melting of different body of knowledge into the paradigms of Nursing helped into the development of its own innovative frameworks.

According to Romero (2011a):

“Nursing as a science has its goal of developing a body of knowledge to be used as basis for nursing practice in a variety of settings. Nursing knowledge, however, is not isolated or exclusive, but rather encompasses the selection, integration, and expansion of knowledge from nursing and other disciplines and the application of this knowledge to the understanding of health and illness and to the analysis and improvement of nursing practice.”

Inasmuch as these learnt concepts borrowed and shared (Polit & Beck, 2008) from other discipline helped in the development of nursing theories, there is a necessity to be aware of that doctoral tutelage for nursing should be in nursing science (Tomey & Alligood, 2002) and not based from other-discipline. This will help differentiate nursing from other professions (Sitzman & Eichelberger, 2004).

“Nursing theory defines and enriches the practice of nursing. It focuses attention on issues essential to providing care. It implies criteria with which to evaluate what nurses do. It presents concepts capable of supporting research most useful to nurses. Thereby it helps create knowledge unique to nursing, thus augmenting the status of nursing as a profession. In fostering research,

nursing theory upholds nursing education, maintaining it on a par with other academic disciplines (Drwiega, n.d.)."

The theory-building development was instigated in the late 1970's (Winters & Lee, 2010). Insofar as nursing education targets principally to train competent nurses, it depends on theory. In structuring doctoral nursing education, nursing theory will be drawn from the essential elements of nursing, including the: (1) patient; (2) environment; (3) provision of nursing care; and (4) health. Elements in nursing education, according to NCSBN (2006), also focus on: (1) curriculum; (2) characteristics of faculty; and (3) program characteristics. Specifically, curriculum elements comprise clinical, didactic and interdisciplinary activities. Theory-based way of approaching the problems with which nurses typically deal structures the standard. In nursing's journey as a profession, it needs a body of knowledge unique to itself from other discipline. Developing nursing theory and supporting theory-based research contributes to building that body of knowledge (Drwiega, n.d.).

Romero (2011a) claimed that:

"While there are different program and title offerings, it is a fact that doctoral study in nursing is built upon and expands the doctoral student's knowledge acquired in baccalaureate and master's degree programs in nursing. Doctoral nursing programs are based on nursing's distinct body of knowledge, which can and must be verified using methods of scholarly inquiry — research. This prepares intellectual leaders with analytical skills to contribute to the development of nursing science. Students bring to doctoral study unique combinations of experiences, knowledge and capabilities that help facilitate an emphasizes on the interchange among clinical practice, research, and teaching based on the belief that research informs practice, practice informs research and both inform teaching."

In the Philippines, as cited by Romero (2011b), not numerous nurses, even nursing leaders hold a doctoral degree in nursing. There are a number of identified factors that was attributed to such phenomena. However, Romero further highlighted that the inadequate number of nursing schools offering a doctorate degree in nursing could be the prime factor. Herewith, many nurses have decided on to expand their scope by taking up alternative doctoral programs such as Doctor of Management, Doctor of Public Health, Doctor of Philosophy in Educational, Doctor of Psychology and Doctor of Education.

There is a need to document the existing scenario of the doctoral nursing program in Cebu City. Documenting the sentiments of nurses on their felt need to expedite doctoral nursing offerings in the area must be transcribed. This literature will be useful for nursing leaders and nursing schools in their plan to improve and act on the current need for advance nursing education. This manuscript attempts to stimulate a fruitful action in revolutionizing doctoral nursing education in the area.

Related to the concerns enumerated above, other relevant and debatable issues can be raised. What if nurses are taking doctoral degrees that are not specific for the nursing profession? Can this improve the poor percentage of nurses with doctorate degrees? Is it necessary to take vertical degrees in nursing? This paper does not attempt to answer any of these questions. But it will provide germane descriptions on nurses in Cebu city taking non-nursing doctorate degrees. These descriptions will stimulate insights that may indirectly provide answers to the questions that I enumerated, allowing the reader to formulate personal and subjective understanding on the current situation in the doctoral nursing education in Cebu city.

II. DOMAIN OF INQUIRY

The purpose of the study was to explore the lived-experiences of nurses taking non-nursing doctoral programs and the reasons behind their choices. Furthermore, it attempted to identify

the weaknesses, demands and scenario of the doctoral nursing offering in the area.

III. ATHEORETICAL STANCE

I employed a naturalistic approach (Royse, 1999) and follow an atheoretical stance (theoretical framework in abeyance) vis-à-vis the phenomenon of interest. Utilizing a highly inductive process (Thomas, 2003; Schriver, 2001), I did not anchor my study in any frameworks and suspended a *priori* conceptualization (Luckerhoff & Guillemette, 2011), otherwise known as substantive theory – that might bias the collection and analysis of data (Polit & Beck, 2008). With this assumption, I also suspended the review of related literature and studies (Polit & Beck, 2008; Berg, 2001).

Furthermore, since I am utilizing Descriptive Husserlian Phenomenology as a research tradition, I did not identify a theory that will support the study and neither did I interpret the results. Descriptive Phenomenology emphasized the description of data only without interpretation: letting the fact speak for itself or of knowledge independent from interpretation (McCance & Mcilpatrick, 2008). Literature review to support the claim may be done to substantiate the description of the phenomenon. However, for this study, I find difficulty in looking for available published articles on doctorate in nursing.

IV. PHILOSOPHICAL STANCE

I trailed the naturalistic paradigm observing the following assumptions (Creswell, 2007; Polit & Beck, 2008): (1) ontologically, reality is multiple and subjective relative to each actor and must be measured from the actor's lenses – this means that I, as the main instrument, need to bracket out my personal interpretations (Walters, 1995; Paley, 1997; Ray, 1985); (2) epistemologically, I and the informants are dependent from each other where interaction is required to gather relevant information; (3) axiologically, values are inevitable and desired providing thick description; and (4) rhetorically, personalistic style of writing required reflexivity and

positioning of myself. This explains why I utilize the first person's voice in this article to emphasize the positioning system. Webb (2009) in Wiley-Blackwell's Writing for publication booklet, and the APA's (2010) Publication manual, preferred the use of personal pronoun to circumvent vagueness particularly in describing activities. The directness in the approach of personal noun eludes puzzlement. The use of personal pronouns hitherto was uniquely for qualitative research (Polit & Beck, 2008), however contemporary journals advocate its use even with quantitative methodologies.

V. METHOD

Design. I followed the phenomenological tradition (Creswell, 2007). I trailed an inductive method (Berg, 2001). Instead of transforming it into operationally defined behavior, it described the phenomenon as experienced by the nurses taking non-nursing doctoral degrees. In descriptive Husserlian phenomenology (McCance & Mcilpatrick, 2008), authenticity is closeness to the phenomenon under investigation. It only focused on description and explanation (Ray, 1985). Phenomenological reduction (Annells, 1999) and bracketing (Wall, Glenn, Mitchinson & Poole, 2004) was deliberately observed.

Sampling of Informants. The criterion-based purposive sample included 10 nurses from Cebu City taking non-doctoral nursing programs. Exclusion criteria in the sample were nurses who had taken doctoral units in nursing. Directions for the study and informed consent were obtained. Data saturation was reached with 10 informants and with my judgment, considering the concept of the researcher as the main instrument (Jackson, Daly & Davidson, 2008); I decided to stop recruiting to avoid data contamination.

Each participant was asked to describe their experience as a nurse pursuing a non-nursing doctoral degree program in as much details as possible. Preliminary findings were validated and the final results were reviewed.

Procedure. I obtained approval from the Research, Planning, Development Department

of the University of the Visayas. Data collection extended for a year through personal interviews, group discussions, phone calls, chat rooms and emails.

I interviewed each participant for 20-60 minutes and all interviews were tape-recorded. The interviews were transcribed and coded to manage the data systematically. Recorded interviews were destroyed after transcription. To avoid any possible bias, I tried to collect the data precisely from those participants yielding authentic data. Data were confirmed using different triangulation techniques. Trustworthiness was enhanced thru (Polit & Beck, 2008): (1) prolonged engagement; (2) persistent observation and reflection; (3) member checking from participants; and (4) audit trail by external experts.

Spending a considerable amount of time with the informants until trust was gained ensured the authenticity of the data collected. Persistent observation and reflection ensured credibility and dependability of the data being gathered. Member checking from participants and audit trail by external experts ensured the confirmability of results.

Asking the same question at different time-points warranted time triangulation. Data saturation of a certain phenomenon from different informants enabled person triangulation. Interviews, observation and reflection were observed to facilitate method triangulation.

Data Analysis. I utilized the Colaizzi's (1978) approach by carefully questioning presuppositions about the phenomenon under investigation. I started by asking general leading questions and once such questions were answered, I then scrutinized and examined these presuppositions. The method for data analysis consisted of seven stages: (1) read and reread all the participants' verbatim transcripts of the phenomena in order to acquire a feeling of them; (2) significant statements or phrases were extracted from the participants' transcripts pertaining directly to the research phenomena; (3) formulated meanings were constructed

from the significant statements; (4) formulated meanings were arranged into clusters and themes which evolved into emergent themes; (5) results were incorporated into a rich and exhaustive description of the lived-experience; (6) exhaustive description for the participants involved in the research were validated; and (7) any new or pertinent data obtained from the participants' validation were incorporated and adapted to attain congruence with the lived experience of the participants studied.

VI. RESULTS

Profile of Doctoral Program in Nursing in the Area. Doctoral nursing program in Cebu City had just started recently with one graduate as of 2012. Only one school is offering the program Doctor of Science in Nursing with the major of Gerontology. There is no other school available in the area. However, in Region VII – Central Visayas, two other schools are offering doctoral nursing program namely: (1) Doctor of Philosophy, Major in Nursing; and (2) Doctor of Nursing Science. However, one must have to travel across water or by air to attend classes and finish the degree.

Limited Offering. Testimonies of nurses taking non-doctoral nursing programs reported that there are only limited offerings for doctoral programs in nursing. In fact, there is only one school in Cebu City offering the program of Doctor of Science in Nursing, Major in Gerontology. Most nurses who wanted to pursue a doctoral degree were not interested with the major offered. Given this scenario, nurses opted to take doctoral programs that are more or less in line with their interest. Doctoral degree such as: (1) Doctor in Education, Major in Science Education; (2) Doctor in Management, Major in Human Resource Management; and (3) Doctor of Philosophy in Education, Major in Research and Evaluation.

The enumerated majors were identified because these are in-line with their current practices and majors in their masteral degree. Parallelism in practice and verticalization of majors were issues identified by the informants. However, this undertaking is not feasible by the

current situation in the area.

"... I wanted to take a doctoral degree in line with nursing leadership and management but there is no offering ... I would rather take a doctoral degree in management than taking a major in Gerontology..." (DM HRM student)

"... Had there been a doctoral degree in psychiatric nursing, I would gladly enroll in the program ... But I am not very interested with the care for the elderly ... I would rather choose a major second to my heart ... nursing research is my second choice that is why I took up a major similar to it ..." (PhD RE student)

"... I am in nursing education for most of my life ... since I am in the nursing academe – I am taking Doctor of Education ... there is no doctoral program for nursing education major ..." (EdD student)

Though there are few offerings in the region, it was observed that **there is only one doctoral nursing program in the city**. There are only few in the region because **there are only few qualified professors**. In addition to that, the sole professor in the city is only a visiting professor from the northern part of the country.

In order for one to take a doctoral degree that is aligned to nursing aside from Gerontology as a major, one has to be educated outside Cebu City (regionally, nationally or internationally). Most nurses cannot afford this considering the remuneration they are currently receiving.

"... How I wish I can get a grant to get a doctoral degree in nursing in the field that I love... this remains a dream ... after applying competitive-based international scholarship... the chances is more than super slim... after considering personal funding... the idea seems to be a joke... that would mean I will not eat at all just to get a degree..."

Nurses do not make much money in Cebu City compared to the remuneration nurses receive overseas. Educational grants are near to impossible and most grants, if not all, oblige grantees to be full time students – and nurses in the area cannot afford not to work since they have a family to support.

Educational financial support is difficult especially when these nurses are using their personal funds. Nurses confided their interest to take doctoral degree in nursing when the privilege is at reach. However, matching their interest and specialization to non-nursing doctoral degree program that is readily available is the best option they can think of for the mean time.

The Need to Take Non-Nursing Doctoral Degree. Though all of the informants are interested in taking a doctoral degree in nursing. Interest as a motivation in taking doctoral degree in nursing was constrained by internal and external factors that pushed them to take non-nursing doctoral programs. The following were identified push factors:

Retention and Competition. Currently, the career of nursing education is very competitive. With the surplus of nurses, nursing schools are closing and some schools have very low enrolment. With this scenario, most schools had employee retrenchment. With the fear of being retrenched, a good number of nurse educators are currently taking a doctoral program for retention purposes. Educational qualification is usually the first criteria to be considered for retention. The priority is to take any doctoral degree. The area of concentration is just a secondary priority. Any doctoral degree is a need for survival.

"There is a great need for continuing education ... the competition is high and I should be ahead from the rest in order to survive ... the major does not matter ... I should have a doctoral degree ... whatever degree it is as long as its doctoral ..."

It is not only about competing for retention; it is also ammunition for the competitive world.

In order for one to stay in the position, one must be equipped with the degree. For those who are aspiring for the position, one must be armed for the spot.

"... because of my managerial position I need to have the doctoral degree in management ... I need to be competitive ... I need to stay in the position ... I must be academically ahead from the rest ... To stay in this competitive word one must be prepared ... It would had been better if there is a doctoral degree for nursing administration and management ..." (Dean)

"... I am aspiring for a higher position ... I need to have a doctoral degree in management ... I was planning to take a doctoral degree for nursing administration and management ... but it is not offered here in Cebu City" (aspiring Dean)

This is not only the case for those nurses currently working. It was also observed that nurses who had never landed into a nursing job are currently taking graduate studies to be competitive. They are taking masteral and even doctoral degree to be ahead from the rest.

"... I am an unemployed registered nurse... I have to take advance studies to widen my chances of getting hired..."

Personal and Professional Growth.

The doctoral program is a good avenue for professional growth experience: (1) familiarity with the important theories; (2) development of a set of research skills; and (3) relationships with professors and fellow doctoral students.

"Even though I am not taking a doctoral program in nursing ... the degree I am taking right now enriched my familiarity with diverse theoretical frameworks that can be adapted to the nursing discipline ... my

exposure to different research methodologies and procedures is of great help ... my mentors have outstanding inputs that can be applied to nursing ... the exchanges of experience with my classmates are worth learning ... However, it would had been better if the program I am currently taking is aligned to the nursing field since some applications discussed were really not related to nursing ... the experiences and example were not in nursing, thus processing them were more difficult than when these things were nursing-related ..."

In as much as there is a lot to learn in non-nursing doctoral program, nurses are still conveying the need to have aligned degrees in nursing to facilitate a better learning experience. When the program is into nursing, the doctoral student will be able to ground himself/herself to the program and will be able to apply these things effectively into practice.

Career Pathing. Though most nurses are taking their doctoral program that is more or less nearer to their chosen nursing career paths, some nurses are realigning or preparing themselves to work outside of the nursing discipline. This is still related to the effects of the surplus of nurses in the country. Vacancies are no longer available and competitions are getting tougher.

"With the trend now that most nursing schools are cutting off employees, I need to be prepared for the future... I need to have a fall back in my career... in case it would be difficult to land in a job in nursing ... then maybe I can work in another field ..."

When other countries are experiencing shortage of nurses, the Philippines, especially in Cebu City is experiencing surplus of nurses. With this scenario, most nurses are realigning their career path either: (1) to land in a job; or (2) preparing to land in a non-nursing-related job in the near future.

Few Scholarship for Doctoral Education Outside Cebu City. Solutions to take a doctoral

degree in nursing can be solved when funding is available. However, funding nurses to study abroad or in any part of the Philippines is remotely possible. Nurses cannot identify scholarship programs. If any, it is highly competitive among nations.

"I wanted to be educated outside of the country so that I can bring back things that I have learnt to my country. But applying for a scholarship is really difficult especially for a doctoral program in nursing... How I wish I had enough resources to support myself... It is really my dream... but not my priority... I have a family to feed..."

Nurses would rather work than grabbing the opportunity for scholarships since they have a family to feed. This is another reality considered by nurses. To get educated in a doctoral program in another country remains to be a dream and not a priority.

Practicality and Convenience that Leads to In-breeding. Most nurse educators are taking the doctoral degree program offerings of their school for practical reasons. Most schools are giving free tuition fees for their employees. Most nurses are grabbing this opportunity for professional growth. But these nurses are forced to take the doctoral programs offered by the institution. They have to match their nursing interest with the most similar program offered.

"Actually I do not have a choice; it is not offered in my school ... so I just decided to enroll in a different program offered by my institution since we are given free tuition fee for 9 units per semester... I hope my school can offer a doctoral program in nursing soon."

"I do not have a choice. If I have to enroll in another school ... I have to pay the entire amount..."

In-breeding is one of the disadvantages in taking a doctoral program offered by the

institution the nurse is working. This hinders the nurse's opportunity in seeing the broad outlook necessary for academic achievement. They cannot bring new ideas into their institution. Their inputs are limited since it is already existent in their institution. Therefore, advancements in both the institution and individual are compromised.

"... I am taking a non-nursing doctorate degree in the institution that I am working. I feel that I do not learn much and that things tackled about are those that I already know. What is new to learn? I am beginning to question myself..."

Potential Danger in Taking Non-Nursing Doctoral Program. Though it is recognized that taking non-nursing theoretical preparations broadened and improved the practice of nursing, this can also lead to some perilous effects. Although it is also possible that solution to nursing concerns may be addressed by theories from other discipline, it is also equally conceivable that nurses may utilize solutions that are not germane to nursing. Directing answers to the problem may be masked by interventions that are not appropriate to nursing and eventually jeopardize the system. It is also possible that the demarcation between the shared (borrowed from other discipline) and the pure nursing concept may lead to an overlap of responsibilities. Overlapping of responsibilities that may eventually cause conflicts in the near future.

"... I am not really sure if what I am taking right now is useful in nursing. Maybe not now ... maybe in the near future ... and maybe never..."

There are always two sides in every coin and there is no definite formula for each action. But this argument is necessary to provide awareness to certain possibilities. This will help remind nurses to be extra careful in their nursing career actions and decisions.

"... One thing I have recognized in my decision is that nurses must take conscientious and deliberate time in choosing what to take for a doctorate degree... You might just regret the consequences and maybe you will realize that it was a waste of time, money and effort ..."

Reasons for the Constraints in Taking the Program. The following reasons were identified: (1) the need to have qualified professors; (2) majority of the schools are not interested to invest; (3) financial constraints; and (4) familial consideration.

Need to Have Qualified Professors. The prime reason for the few offerings is brought about by the few qualified professors to teach doctoral courses in nursing. This need is identified among informants with the following expressed solutions: (1) inviting qualified professors to teach in the city; and (2) sending doctoral students to study in other places. Graduates of doctoral degree in nursing from any of these expressed solutions can contribute to the pool of qualified professors in the area. Either ways, institutions can potentially open doctoral nursing degrees. However, this alone cannot warrant its viability. In fact, solution number 1 was pioneered by one of the state universities in the area. However, there are only few takers due to the offering – nurses chose not to take Geriatrics as the Major. Hopefully, solution number 2 can be explored in the near future and/or solution number 1 can still be done with a more viable offering.

"There are only few qualified professors and that is why there is only one offering..."

Majority of the Schools are Not Interested to Invest. Schools are not interested in offering the program. Hiring qualified professors from outside Cebu and sending students abroad is an investment – it is currently not the priority. Viability of the program was one of the considerations for the disinterest. Currently, no studies were conducted to determine its viability.

Though one school is interested to invest, they have a problem in recruiting qualified professors for the more appealing offering.

"... With the current trend in the Philippines where there are pool of untapped nurses either displaced or unemployed, I think colleges and universities are not interested in opening doctorate programs in nursing... They are afraid if there are no takers... Education is business and school owners are also businessmen... I think you know what I mean..."

Financial Constraints. Getting a degree outside Cebu is an option. But for most, this is not the priority due to financial reasons. Most of those interested have families to support. The need of the family is the top most priority and getting the doctoral degree is only secondary. Though getting a scholarship is an option, it is highly competitive. Most of the time, they do not get picked and the majority does not even get to try to apply.

"... I am a mother with studying kids. I need to prioritize their needs..."

"... I wanted to study abroad... It is sad that my resources cannot allow me to fulfill that dream. I also tried applying scholarships... it is also very sad that I do not get short-listed..."

Familial Consideration. Among Cebuanos, the family is a treasure. It is cogitated as very important and it is always prioritized. Aside from economic consideration, familial protection and preservation is highly embellished by being together. Studying away from home is a sacrifice. Most cannot afford to disharmonize a protected treasure not unless they get income out from it. Income itself is for the family.

"... I am a mother with studying kids... I also need to be at their side. They are still growing and it is my responsibility to take care of them..."

"It is good to finish a doctorate degree. Here or abroad, it does not matter. This will give me an opportunity to climb up the ladder... this means more income for my family."

Viability of Opening Doctoral Programs in Nursing. As previously reported, the interest of nurses in taking doctoral degree in nursing was constrained due to the limited offerings in the area. Multiple reasons were identified in the selection of the alternative. Though transferability (equivalent to generalizability in quantitative studies) of results can be claimed, not enough evidence can warrant statistical generalizability due to the weakness in sampling – just like any other qualitative researches. However, this does not mean that the results are of poor quality. The intention of this research is only to describe and provide a conceptual underpinning that can be utilized as a foundation in conducting a quantitative research with good statistical sampling representativeness. It is not the intention to prove statistically generalizable results. Furthermore, it was not the intention to determine the feasibility in opening doctoral nursing programs in the area. However, it is a noble jump-start in conducting highly methodological investigation with the objective of determining its viability.

The possibility of opening other majors can only be realized if the four enumerated constraints can be addressed. Though the opened major in Gerontology is not an appetitive offering in the area, it is a good start to provide access to a doctoral degree in nursing. It was identified that there are only few takers and that they took the program because it was the only rational choice. Lucidly, the opening of the sole major is a: (1) good indicator that other majors can be offered in the near future; and (2) precursor in identifying the need of offering more desirable programs with good number of interested takers.

VII. WRAPPING-UP

Nurses confessed the need to open doctoral majors in nursing that are aligned to their

current career, practice and masteral majors. The deficiency of qualified professors and disinterest of investment among institutions constrained the opening of other majors. Furthermore, financial constraints, inaccessibility to scholarships and familial considerations hindered nurses to take offerings from other places.

It is also sad to note that some nurses are slowly realigning their vocations to non-nursing career-paths. This is another issue that nursing leaders and the government should take into deliberate consideration. If this will pursue, their potentials will not be of use – adding them to the count of untapped human resource in nursing. Their capabilities could have been utilized to upgrade the current developing nursing system.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The core phenomenon emanates the need to revolutionize doctoral nursing education in the region and in the country. This revolution does not only call for attaining personal interests but to uplift the standard of the profession beyond the need of the self. With the challenge for the development of needed highly developed competencies for progressively more complex clinical, faculty and leadership roles, nurses are challenged to enhance nursing knowledge to improve practice. Provision of an advanced educational credential for those who require advanced practice knowledge requires educational training and exposure aligned to their field and practice. With the call for transformation and advancement in nursing and its practice, nurses must grow professionally by taking doctoral program in different nursing concentrations and not with other or related disciplines.

I will recommend that universities and nursing faculties must provide agendas to advocate in the advancement of doctoral nursing degree in the region and the country. This advocacy must focus on transforming the profession afar from individual welfares. Further studies will be conducted to: (1) validate the results utilizing quantitative research methodology with good sampling technique; and (2) identify the viability

of opening other doctoral programs in nursing in the area. Nursing schools and associations should provide options and access to national and international scholarship grants to deserving candidates.

Originality Index:	90 %
Similarity Index:	10 %
Paper ID:	341977258
Grammarly:	Checked

REFERENCES

- American Association of Colleges of Nursing (2004). *AACN position statement on the practice doctorate in nursing: October 2004*. Retrieved last October 1, 2011 from <http://www.aacn.nche.edu/DNP/pdf/DNP.pdf>
- American Psychological Association (2010). *Publication manual of the American Psychological Association (6th Ed.)*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association Press.
- Annels, M. (1999). Evaluating phenomenology: Usefulness, quality and philosophical foundations. *Nurse Researcher*, 6(3), 5-19.
- Berg, B. L. (2001). *Qualitative research for the social sciences (4th Ed.)*. Needham Heights, MA: A Pearson Education Company.
- Colaizzi, P. (1978). Psychological research as the phenomenologist views it. In Valle, R., & King, M. (Ed.), *Existential phenomenological alternatives for psychology* (pp. 48-71). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions (2nd Ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cronenwett, L. (2010). *The future of nursing education*. Paper commissioned by the Committee on the RWJF Initiative on the Future of Nursing at the IOM. Washington, DC: Institute of Medicine.
- Drwiega, M. (n.d.). *Importance of nursing theory in education*. Retrieved last October 1, 2011 from http://www.ehow.com/about_6602155_importance-nursing-theory-education.html#ixzz1e6BHSrfz
- East Asian Forum on Nursing Scholars (2012). *Advancing doctoral nursing programmes in East Asia: Contribution to nursing*. May 21, 2012 from <http://medicine.nus.edu.sg/nursing/events/eafons-aprs2012/>
- Feeg, V., & Nickitas, V. M. (2011). Doubling the number of nurses with a doctorate by 2020: Predicting the right number or getting it right? *Nursing Economics*, 29(3), 109-110 & 125.
- George, J. (2002). *Nursing theories: The base for professional nursing practice (5th ed.)*. Norwalk, CT: Appleton & Lange.
- Institute of Medicine (2010). *The future of nursing: Leading change, advancing health*. Washington, DC.
- Jackson, D., Daly, J., & Davidson, P. (2008). Interviews. In Watson, R., McKenna, H., Cowman, S., & Keady, J. (Ed.). *Nursing research: Designs and methods* (pp. 281-288). Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier Limited.
- Luckerhoff, J., & Guillemette, F. (2011). The conflicts between Grounded Theory requirements and institutional requirements for scientific research. *The Qualitative Report*, 16(2), 396-414. Retrieved May 21, 2012 from <http://www.nova.edu/ssss/QR/QR16-2/luckerhoff.pdf>
- McCance, T., & McIlpatrick, S. (2008). Phenomenology. In Watson, R., Mckenna, H., Cowman, S., & Keady, J. (Ed.) *Nursing research: Designs and methods* (pp. 231-242). Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier Limited.
- National Council of State Boards of Nursing (2006). A national survey on elements of nursing education. *NCsbn Research Brief*, 24.
- Paley, J. (1997). Husserl, phenomenology and nursing. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 26, 187-193.
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2008) *Nursing research: generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice (8th Ed.)*. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Ray, M. A. (1985). A philosophical method to study nursing phenomena. In Leininger, M. M. (Ed.), *Qualitative research methods in nursing* (pp. 81-92). Orlando: Grune & Stratton.
- Republic Act No. 9173 (2002). *Philippine Nursing Act of 2002*.
- Romero, B. W. (2011a). *Doctoral nursing programs: Advancing nursing perspective*. Retrieved last October 3, 2011 from <http://nursingcrib.com/nursing-program/doctoral-nursing-programs-advancing-nursing-perspective/>
- Romero, B. W. (2011b). *Schools offering doctoral nursing programs in the Philippines*. Retrieved last October 3, 2011 from <http://nursingcrib.com/nursing-schools/schools-offering-doctoral-nursing-programs-in-the-philippines/>
- Royse, D. (1999). *Research methods in social work (3rd Ed.)*. Chicago: Nelson-Hall Publishers.
- Schriver, J. M. (2001). *Human behavior in the social environment: Shifting paradigms in essential knowledge for social work practice (3rd Ed.)*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Sitzman, K., & Eichelberger, L. W. (2004). *Understanding the work on nursing theorists*. Sudbury, MA: Jones & Bartlett Publishers, Inc.
- Thomas, D. R. (2003). A general inductive approach for qualitative data analysis. *School of Population Health*. Retrieved May 21, 2012 from http://www.fmhs.auckland.ac.nz/soph/centres/hrmas/_docs/Inductive2003.pdf

- Tomey, A. M., & Alligood, M. R. (2002). *Nursing theorists and their work* (5th Ed.). St. Louis: Mosby Inc.
- Wall, C., Glenn, S., Mitchison, S., & Poole, H. (2004). Using a reflective diary to develop bracketing skills during phenomenological investigation. *Nurse Researcher*, 11(4), 20-28.
- Walters, A. J. (1995). The phenomenological movement: implications for nursing research. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 22, 791-799.
- Webb, C. (2009). *Writing for publication*. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Winters, C. A., & Lee, H. J. (2010). *Rural nursing: Concepts, theory, and practice* (3rd Ed.). New York: Springer Publishing Company.